

**CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE FACTORS OF SELF-AWARENESS,
SELF-REGULATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF POST-BASIC STUDENTS IN
CHEMISTRY IN ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study probed the correlation between self-awareness and self-regulation factors of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. Correlational research design was adopted for the study and grounded in Goleman's emotional intelligence model. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses provided the framework for the study. The population of the study was the entire 4,500 Post-Basic III students who offered Chemistry in 2022/2023 session. A sample of 452 students were selected from 21 schools through multistage random sampling technique. Emotional Self-Awareness and Regulation Scale (ESARS), was used to survey the emotional intelligence of the participants while Chemistry Academic Achievement Pro forma (CAAP) was used to retrieve the participants' academic achievement scores. Mean and standard deviation were used to address the research questions, simple linear regression was used to test the first and second hypotheses, while multiple regression was used to test the third hypothesis all at .05 significance threshold. Findings revealed that there is high positive correlation between self-awareness ($r = .631$, $p < .05$), self-regulation ($r = .672$, $p < .05$), emotional intelligence ($r = .678$, $p < .05$), [$F(2, 451) = 190.963$] and academic achievement. It was recommended among others that emotional intelligence instructions be incorporated into the guidance and counseling programme to enable students understand their thoughts, motives, desires, strengths and weaknesses; and make career choices that align with their interests and capabilities.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Self-Awareness, Self-Regulation, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Science and technology (Chemistry inclusive), is an indispensable and the most effective catalyst required to drive progress in all the facets of human endeavours. George (2021), noted that scientific knowledge and skills and technological advancements are essential drivers for breakthroughs in agriculture, communication, industries and medicine; and for addressing global challenges such as climate change, ecological impact of modern technology, genetic engineering and nuclear threats among others. Being a united and self-reliant nation, is one of the national goals of Nigeria (FGN, 2013). For Nigeria to attain such a lofty ideal, it is imperative for the government to prioritize science and technology in its education, invest generously in it and ensure students' academic success in science subjects to fully harvest the accruing benefits.

Grading is one of the fundamentals of educational assessment in many countries including Nigeria; providing a quantitative measure of students' academic achievement that informs high stakes decisions like university admission (Brookhart et al., 2016). It therefore means that Nigeria must prioritize its citizen's achievement in science and technology subjects; ensuring they meet admission requirements to pursue these fields in higher education in order to experience technological advancements. Unfortunately, the academic achievement of students in Chemistry in external examinations such as WAEC has been unsatisfactory over the years. The World Bank (2020) blames Nigeria's poor education quality, resulting in low academic achievement to factors including inadequate infrastructures, instructional materials, teacher incompetence, insufficient classrooms, limited access to ICT tools and teacher absenteeism. However, interventions made by successive governments of Adamawa state in these areas failed to yield the desired outcomes. Analysis of WAEC results for the years ranging from 2018-2022, shows that only 53.38% of candidates who sat for Chemistry obtained at least a credit (Adamawa State Planning Commission, 2023).

Given that some students excel in Chemistry under similar conditions; the researchers are compelled to explore other potential factors influencing academic achievement within the learner such as emotional intelligence. According to Lauren (2019), emotional intelligence involves managing one's own emotions and understanding and impacting the emotions of others. The Goleman's (1998) seminal emotional intelligence model delineates five components namely: self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. Notably the first three components pertain to personal skills whereas the latter two encompass social aptitudes. This study explored the self-awareness and self-regulation facets of personal skills as they constitute the foundational pillars that illuminate the intrinsic mechanisms that underpin emotional intelligence and its consequential effect on diverse outcomes (Alan, 2018).

Self-awareness as defined by Eurich (2018), involves having a deeper understanding of one's characteristics, desires, feelings, interests and motives. Goleman (1998) opined that students who are self-aware can identify their strengths and weaknesses; develop strategies to overcome their inadequacies leading to improved academic achievement. Self-awareness is also essential for individuals to make better decisions, establish and build stronger relationships and experience personal growth. In addition to self-awareness, effective stress and frustration management skills are also crucial for academic and success in all works of life.

Self-regulation involves perceiving, managing and responding to frustrations (Goleman, 1998). Students who adapt to every situation, and effectively manage challenges confronted in schools outperform their counterparts with poor stress management skills. Sahvanavard et al. (2018) submits that students with high self-regulation scores employ adaptive strategies necessary to excel in schools. When students combine self-awareness with self-regulation, they can develop the skill sets for the achievement of their academic and overall personal goals.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Chemistry being one of the subjects taught at the Post-Basic Schools in Nigeria, plays a significant role in Nigeria's economic well-being and serves as a prerequisite for science and technology courses in higher education. This underscores the need for Chemistry not only be taught but for students to strive to excel in it. However, recent statistics from Adamawa state reveal a dismal trend of poor academic achievement in Chemistry among students; with only an average of 53.38% of students achieving at least a credit pass and above between 2018 and 2022 (Adamawa State Planning Commission, 2023). This is however not surprising due to the continuous classification of Adamawa state among the educationally backward

states in Nigeria (Joint Admission and Matriculation Board, 2023). It therefore demands that concerted effort be made by relevant stakeholders to ameliorate this negative trend of poor academic achievement for Adamawa state to compete with and stand tall in the comity of states, in science and technology related courses in the tertiary institutions of learning. Regrettably, efforts made by successive governments of Adamawa state to address this problem in areas of staffing, training and retraining of teachers, provision of laboratories and other instructional materials seem not to have yielded the much-desired result. Hence, the need to explore other factors such as emotional intelligence given that some students excel in Chemistry under the same conditions of teaching and learning in schools. Emotional intelligence is a factor which draws on both the external environmental factors as well as genetic predispositions of a person. While the later may not be easily alterable through intervention, the former aspect of emotional intelligence can be mediated through intervention such as instruction or training.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study investigates the relationship between emotional intelligence and students' achievement in Adamawa state.

The study specifically examined the relationships between:

1. Self-awareness and students' academic achievement in Chemistry.
2. Self-regulation and students' academic achievement in Chemistry.
3. Emotional intelligence and students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were answered:

1. What is the level of self-awareness of students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?
2. What is the level of self-regulation of students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?
3. What is the mean academic achievement score of students in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?

HYPOTHESES

The three stated null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant correlation between self-awareness and students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

HO₂: There is no significant correlation between self-regulation and students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

HO₃: There is no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is underpinned to Goleman's (1998) emotional intelligence model, specifically focusing on self-awareness (intrapersonal awareness) and self-regulation (self-management/stress management/emotional management/managing emotions). Goleman (1998), observed that self-aware individuals can set clear unambiguous goals; show self-confidence and enthusiasm for problem-solving. This concept is supported by Duval and Wicklund's (1972) self-awareness theory which posits that self-focused individuals tend to compare themselves to standards and strive to meet those

standards. Self-regulation involves managing internal impulses, maintaining integrity and handling disruptive emotions (Goleman, 1998). Research had shown a positive relationship between self-awareness, self-regulation and academic achievement, with studies by Razia and Ahmad (2017), Amalu (2018), Sahvanavard et al. (2018), Adigwe (2015), Ebinagbome and Nizam (2016), Khuan and Lin (2021) and Oyewunmi et al. (2016) all reporting significant positive relationships between self-awareness, self-regulation and academic achievement. On the contrary, studies by Prakash and Vasimalairaja (2021) and Ngu et al. (2016), found no significant relationship between self-awareness, self-regulation and academic achievement.

The empirical literature review highlights varying findings on the correlation between the variables of the study across different subject areas, geographical niches and educational levels. While some studies reported significant positive findings, others found no significant relationships between self-awareness, self-regulation and academic achievement. The reviewed studies predominantly focused on secondary schools (62.50%) with only few from universities (25%) and colleges of education (12.50%), stressing the need for research at the primary schools, colleges of education and universities. Notably, only three Nigerian studies were reviewed, with just one conducted in Northern Nigeria, specifically in Mathematics. Significantly, no studies on emotional intelligence were found from Adamawa state either in digital or print form; hence stressing the significance of this study in bridging the lacuna in the existing literature of this kind.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between self-awareness and self-regulation components of emotional intelligence and academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. According to Bhandari (2022), correlational research design explores the extent and direction of relationships between variables without control or manipulation. The population of the study was 4,500 Post-Basic III Students who offered Chemistry in the year 2023 (Adamawa State Planning Commission, 2023); while the sample was 452 students drawn from the population by multistage random sampling technique and determined by Yamane's sample size formula (Yamane, 1967).

A 5-Point Likert Type Emotional Self-Awareness and Regulation Scale (ESARS) was adapted from Sandhya and Namrata (2013) to survey the emotional intelligence of the participants. The ESARS was made up of 25 items almost equally divided into two clusters: self-awareness (12 items) and self-regulation (13 items). The ESARS demonstrated high reliability; with an overall coefficient of .94 and subscale coefficients of .89 for self-awareness and .90 for self-regulation all determined by Cronbach alpha. A six-column Chemistry Academic Achievement Pro forma (CAAP) was used to retrieve the participants' academic achievement scores.

Data were collected in three phases spanning 14 days. In the first phase, the researchers introduced themselves to the principals and Chemistry teachers of the sample schools who served as research assistants. The second phase involved distribution of the questionnaires to the research assistants who were told to administer the questionnaires during Chemistry lessons, provide clarification when need be and ensure a 100% return rate; while the questionnaires were retrieved in the third and final phase. The CAAPs were also distributed to the respective Chemistry teachers who supplied the academic achievement scores of the participants. Research questions were addressed using arithmetic mean and standard deviation according to the following: Very High Level (VHL) = 4.50-5.00, High Level (HL) = 3.50-4.49, Moderate Level (ML) = 2.50-3.49, Low Level (LL) = 1.50-2.49 and Very Low Level (VLL) = .50-1.49; simple linear regression was used to test hypotheses one and two while multiple regression was used to test hypothesis three at .05 significance level. A hypothesis is rejected if $p\text{-value} < .05$, otherwise, the null hypothesis is retained.

RESULTS

Three research questions and three null hypotheses were answered and tested respectively in logical sequence of the formulated objectives.

Research Question One

What is the level of self-awareness of students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Self-awareness of Students Offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	Items	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	I recognize how my feelings affect my performance.	4.00	0.82	HL
2	I am aware of my goals.	3.96	0.83	HL
3	I am aware of my strengths	3.94	0.86	HL
4	I am aware of my weaknesses	3.94	0.87	HL
5	I try to learn from experience.	3.95	0.91	HL
6	I am open to continuous learning.	3.97	0.88	HL
7	I am open to new perspectives	3.88	0.97	HL
8	I am organized in discharging my duties.	3.93	0.95	HL
9	I am careful about my work	3.95	0.91	HL
10	I usually go for original ideas while solving problems.	3.94	0.91	HL
11	I am able to make sound decision despite uncertainties.	3.95	0.92	HL
12	I present myself with self-assurance.	3.87	0.98	HL
	Average	3.94		HL

n = 452

key: S.D = Standard Deviation

HL = High Level

Table 1 reveals that students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state exhibited a high level of self-awareness, with an average mean score of 3.94 which indicates a strong awareness for their thoughts, feelings and performance. The extreme means of the individual items ranged from 3.87 to 4.00 for “I am open to new perspectives” and “I recognize how my feelings affect my performance” items respectively.

Research Question Two

What is the level of self-regulation of students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Self-regulation of Students Offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	Items	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	I usually get sad for some reasons or the other.	4.07	0.89	HL
2	I feel happy about my life.	4.00	0.84	HL
3	I am able to make sound decision under pressure.	3.92	0.87	HL

4	I can predict clearly whether my emotion is happy or sad.	3.94	0.89	HL
5	I do not copy other peoples` lifestyle.	3.96	0.83	HL
6	I am a cheerful person.	3.91	0.84	HL
7	I can win over stress without getting nervous.	3.97	0.86	HL
8	I manage disappointment well.	3.94	0.87	HL
9	I keep myself calm even in frustrating situations.	3.89	0.93	HL
10	I remain focused under pressure.	3.89	0.95	HL
11	I am stress free most of the time.	3.97	0.90	HL
12	I do not always control myself when I hear a bad news.	3.87	0.95	HL
13	I usually handle multiple demands according to priorities.	3.90	1.04	HL
	Average	3.94		HL

n = 452

Key: S.D = Standard Deviation

HL = High Level

From Table 2, students offering Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state demonstrate a high level of self-regulation, with an average mean score of 3.94. The means of the individual items consistently fell within 3.87 and 4.07; indicating a high level of students` ability to effectively regulate their thoughts, emotions and behaviours in the face of frustrations and challenges.

Research Question Three

What is the mean academic achievement score of students in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Achievement Scores of Students in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state

	n	Mean	S. D
Students' Academic Achievement	452	55.20	12.95

The analysis in Table 3 reveals that students` mean academic achievement score in Chemistry is 55.20 and standard deviation is 12.95. This suggests that majority of the students performed above average in Chemistry.

Hypothesis One

HO₁: There is no significant correlation between self-awareness and students` academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA of Regression Analysis of Correlation Between Self-Awareness and Students` Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	179.628	1	179.628	297.867	.000 ^b
	Residual	271.372	450	.603		
	Total	451.000	451			

- a. Dependent Variable: Z score: Students' academic achievement
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Self-awareness

The ANOVA results in Table 4a indicate a significant correlation between self-awareness and students' academic achievement in Chemistry, $F_{(1,451)} = 297.867, p < .05$. Since the p-value (0.000) is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying a statistically significant relationship between self-awareness and Chemistry achievement.

Table 4b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Squared	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.631 ^a	.398	.397	.77656216

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-awareness

According to Table 4b, the model summary reveals that there is a high positive relationship between self-awareness and academic achievement ($r = .631, p < .05$). Also, self-awareness accounts for 39.70% of the variance in students' academic achievement in Chemistry, indicating a substantial influence of self-awareness on academic achievement.

Table 4c: Coefficients of Beta

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-3.689	.217		-17.012	.000
	Self-awareness	.938	.054	.631	17.259	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Z score: Students' academic achievement

The regression analysis in Table 4c shows a beta coefficient of .631 ($p < .05$), indicating that self-awareness makes a significant and substantial unique contribution to students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: There is no significant correlation between self-regulation and students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

Table 5a: Summary of ANOVA of Regression Analysis of Correlation Between Self-Regulation and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	203.554	1	203.554	370.180	.000 ^b
	Residual	247.446	450	.550		
	Total	451.000	451			

- a. Dependent Variable: Z score: Students' academic achievement
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Self-regulation.

The ANOVA results in Table 5a indicate a significant correlation between self-regulation and students' academic achievement in Chemistry, $F_{(1, 451)} = 370.180, p < .05$. With a p-value of 0.000, the null hypothesis is rejected implying a statistically significant relationship between self-regulation and academic achievement in Chemistry.

Table 5b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Squared	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.672 ^a	.451	.450	.74153865

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-regulation

Table 5b is the model summary which reveals that there is a high positive relationship between self-regulation and academic achievement ($r = .672, p < .05$). Also, self-regulation explains 45% of the variance in students' academic achievement in Chemistry, indicating a remarkable influence of self-regulation on academic achievement.

Table 5c: Coefficients of Beta

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-5.805	.304		-19.113	.000
	Self-regulation	1.587	.082	.672	19.240	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Z score: Students' academic achievement

Table 5c displays the regression analysis which shows a beta coefficient of .672 ($p < .05$), indicating that self-regulation makes a significant unique contribution to students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

Hypothesis Three

HO₃: There is no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

Table 6a: Summary of ANOVA of Regression Analysis of Correlation Between Emotional Intelligence and Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34760.444	2	17380.222	190.963	.000 ^b
	Residual	40865.032	449	91.013		
	Total	75625.476	451			

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement
- b. Predictors (Constant): Self-awareness, self-regulation

Table 6a indicates a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement in Chemistry, $F_{(2, 451)} = 190.963, p < 0.05$. The null hypothesis is rejected because p-value (0.000) is less than .05.

Table 6b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.678 ^a	.460	.457	9.54010

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-regulation, Self-awareness

The model summary in Table 6b indicates the high positive correlation between emotional intelligence and students' achievement in Chemistry ($r = .678, p < .05$). The table further reveals that emotional intelligence substantially accounts for 45.70% of the variance in students' achievement in Chemistry.

Table 6c: Coefficients of Beta

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-32.655	6.213		-5.256	.000
	Self-awareness	-7.397	2.817	-.384	-2.626	.009
	Self-regulation	31.975	4.478	1.045	7.140	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

Table 6c shows the standardized beta coefficients for the contribution of each of the variables in predicting the students' achievement in Chemistry. It can be deduced that self-awareness and self-regulation explains 38.40% and 104.50% respectively to students' achievement. Self-regulation is therefore a more powerful predictor of students' achievement in Chemistry than self-awareness.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the relationship between self-awareness, self-regulation and academic achievement in Chemistry among students in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The results revealed a high level of self-awareness among students, which significantly correlates with academic achievement in Chemistry. This suggests that students with high level of self-awareness tend to run circles around those with low levels. Specifically, students who set clear goals, identify their interests, strengths and weaknesses are more likely to excel academically. These findings align with the findings of previous research by Ebinagbome and Nizam (2016), Razia and Ahmad (2017), Amalu, (2018), Oyewunmi et al. (2016) who reported a significant relationship between self-awareness and academic achievement. On the contrary, the findings contradict those of Prakash and Vasimalairaja (2021) and Ngu et al. (2016) who both found no significant relationship between self-awareness and academic achievement.

The study also found that students exhibit a high level of self-regulation, which positively correlates with their academic achievement in Chemistry. This suggests that students who are flexible, determined and effectively regulate and adapt to different situations perform academically better than their counterparts with lower levels of self-regulation. These findings are consistent with the findings of previous studies conducted by Adigwe (2015), Ebinagbome and Nizam (2016), Oyewunmi et al. (2016) and Khuan and Lin (2021) who all reported a positive relationship between self-regulation and academic achievement. However, findings of some studies conducted by Ngu et al. (2016), and Prakash and Vasimalairaja (2021) reported no significant association between self-regulation and academic achievement.

Furthermore, the study revealed that there is high positive relationship between emotional intelligence and students' achievement in Chemistry. This implies that students with high levels of self-awareness and self-regulation and demonstrate greater emotional stability achieve high in Chemistry. This agrees with the findings of Amalu (2018) and Ebinagbome and Nizam (2016) who also found similar results on the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. In contrast, Ngu et al. (2016), found no positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that Post-Basic III students who offered Chemistry in Adamawa state in 2022/2023 session exhibited high levels of self-awareness and self-regulation which is evident by their coincidental average mean score of 3.94. Also, the three null hypotheses were all rejected given that the p-values were all below the .05 significance threshold. This implies that self-awareness and self-regulation both had an independent and combined positive significant correlations with academic achievement in Chemistry. Notably, self-regulation emerged as a stronger influence of Chemistry achievement compared to self-awareness. Consequently, it is imperative to consider self-awareness and self-regulation as determinants of Chemistry achievement in Post-Basic schools in Adamawa state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Students should receive self-awareness guidance to recognize their strengths, weaknesses, interests and desires, enabling them to set clear achievable goals. Additionally, parents and teachers should leverage students' self-knowledge to guide and support them in making informed career choices that align with their interests and capabilities.
2. School administrators, parents and teachers should support students to develop self-regulation skills to better cope with frustrations and challenges encountered in schools. Moreover, schools should create a positive and conducive learning environment to reduce stress and frustration among students.
3. Emotional intelligence should be made an integral part of the curriculum, so that students are taught and guided to recognize, understand and effectively manage their frustrations.

REFERENCES

- Adamawa State Planning Commission (2023). Post Primary Schools Management Board Yola. <https://adspc.ad.gov.ng/post-primary-schools-management-board/>
- Adigwe, J. C. (2015). Emotional intelligence and problem-solving achievement of Chemistry students. *ATBU Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 3(1), 80-95.

- Alan, M. (2018). Emotional intelligence: The importance of self-awareness and self-regulation. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com>
- Amalu, M. N. (2018). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of academic performance among secondary school students in Makurdi metropolis of Benue state. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11(1), 63-70.
- Bhandari, P. (2022). *Correlational research: When and how to use it*. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research/>
- Brookhart, S. M., Guskey, T. R., Bowers, A. J. McMilan, J. H. Smith, J. K., Smith, L. F. Stevens, M. T. & Welsh, M. E. (2016). A century of grading research. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 803-848. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465316672069>
- Duval, S. T. & Wicklund, R. A. (1972). *A theory of objective self-awareness*. New York: Academic Press.
- Ebinagbome, M. E. & Nizam, I. (2016). The impact of emotional intelligence on students' academic performance: A study on Malaysian tertiary institution. *International Journal of Accounting and Business Management*, 4 (1), 10-18.
- Eurich, T. (2018). *What self-awareness really means and how to cultivate it*. Harvard Business Review. <https://hbr.org/2018/01/what-self-awareness-really-is-and-how-to-cultivate-it>
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education*. Yaba-Lagos: NERDC press.
- George, M. (2021). Scientific literacy and its importance. Wondorium Daily. <https://www.wondoriumdaily.com/scientific-literacy-and-its-importance/>
- Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (2023). *JAMB admission process 2023 JAMB admission update*. UTME Official. <https://utmeofficial.com.ng/post-utme/jamb-admission-process-2021-jamb-admission-guidelines-update/>
- Khuan, W. S. & Lin, P. K. C. (2021). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of students' academic achievement. *ESTEEM Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(1), 56-66.
- Lauren, L. (2019). Why emotional intelligence is important in leadership. Harvard Business School Online. <https://online.jbs.edu>
- Ngu, L. S., Zahyah, H., Muhajir, T. & Arumugam, R. (2016). Influence of emotional intelligence on students' academic achievements. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Research*, 2(3), 41-46.
- Oyewunmi, A. E., Osinbajo, A. O. & Adeniji, A. A. (2016). Emotional intelligence and academic achievement of undergraduates: Correlations, implications and interactions. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1), 509.
- Prakash, M. J. & Vasimalairaja, M. (2021). Influence of emotional intelligence and lateral thinking on achievement in biology of XI standard students. *Elementary Education Online*, 20(5), 2426-2426.
- Razia, B. & Ahmad, N. (2017). Emotional intelligence and socioeconomic status as determinants of academic achievement among adolescents. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research*, 6(2), 137-142.
- Sahvanavard, S., Miri, M. R. & Selehiniya, H. (2018). The relationship between self-regulation and educational performance in students. *Journal of Educational and Health Promotion*, 7(1), 154.
- Sandhya, M. & Namrata, S. (2013). Development of the emotional intelligence scale. *International Journal of Management and Information Technology*, 8(1), 1252-1264.
- World Bank (2020). *The education crisis: Being in school is not the same as learning*. Washington DC: World Bank
- Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An introductory analysis, 2nd edition*. New York: Harper and Row.